

DEVELOPMENT OF METFORMIN ANALYSIS METHODS FOR JUDICIAL CHEMISTRY PRACTICE

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Annotation. *This study focuses on developing optimal methods for extracting metformin from aqueous environments for use in forensic chemical analysis. Considering the widespread use of metformin in treating Type 2 diabetes and obesity, as well as its inclusion in biologically active supplements, the research addresses the risks associated with improper use and possible poisoning. Various organic solvents and pH levels were tested to determine the most effective extraction conditions. The influence of electrolyte presence and multiple extraction cycles was also evaluated. The proposed method was successfully applied to isolate metformin from biological fluids such as blood and urine using thin-layer chromatography and UV spectrophotometry. The findings confirm that the technique is effective and can be applied in forensic toxicology.*

Keywords: *Metformin extraction, forensic chemistry, organic solvents, pH influence, biological, fluids, thin-layer chromatography, spectrophotometry, toxicology, type 2 diabetes, analytical method development.*

Actuality: According to statistical data, 1.9 billion people worldwide currently face issues related to excess weight, and nearly 450 million people are diagnosed with diabetes. To date, 11 interrelated mechanisms that trigger the development of diabetes are known. Type 2 diabetes arises from a combination of genetic and lifelong factors. Metformin is used as a complex treatment for obesity and to maintain weight in patients with Type 2 diabetes. It is also used as a weight loss agent in various biologically active substances. However, the misuse of such medications can lead to severe poisoning cases.

Goal of the Research: To study the optimal conditions for extracting metformin from an aqueous environment.

Methods and Techniques: Organic solvents such as benzene (GOST 5779-78), diethyl ether (GOST 12375-76), chloroform (P 76.822.279), ethyl acetate (GOST 7137-72), and butanol-1 (GOST 6933-75) were used to study the impact of solvent nature on the extraction process. The pH value of the environment greatly influences the extraction process from an aqueous medium. Therefore, the effect of pH on the extraction of metformin from an aqueous environment was studied. Solutions with pH values of 1.56, 3.56, 4.01, 6.86, 9.18, and 12.45 were prepared using standard fixanals (GOST 8.135 - 74, pH metric standard – titr).

50 ml of each pH solution was taken in a tightly sealed conical flask with a capacity of 250 ml, to which 1 ml of a working solution containing 150 mcg/ml of metformin and 10 ml of organic solvent was added. The mixture was shaken uniformly for 10 minutes on a mechanical shaker. The flasks were then left for 5 minutes to allow layer separation. After complete separation of the layers, the organic solvent layer was collected using a separation funnel, filtered through solvent-moistened filter paper into dry porcelain dishes after adding 5 g of

anhydrous sodium sulfate. The filter paper was washed with 3-5 ml of organic solvent, and the washing was combined with the main extract. The organic solvents extracted from the extract were evaporated under hot air until a dry residue was obtained. The dry residue was dissolved in purified water and brought to 5 ml, and analyzed using UV-spectrophotometry. When metformin was extracted from an aqueous environment with a pH of 9.18, a maximum of 66.0% transferred to the chloroform layer in a single extraction. To study the effect of the number of extractions on the complete transfer of metformin to the organic layer, 2, 3, 4, and 5 extractions with chloroform were carried out. When metformin was re-extracted from the aqueous layer with chloroform 5 times at pH 9.18, a 92.15% extraction efficiency was achieved. The impact of electrolytes on the extraction degree was studied as follows: 10 ml of saturated solutions of sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate were added to 50 ml of aqueous medium containing 1 ml of working solution with 100 mcg/ml of metformin, followed by extraction under the previously described conditions. Metformin extraction from the aqueous medium yielded results of 58.0% in the presence of ammonium sulfate and 61.0% in the presence of sodium chloride.

Results: The obtained analysis results were applied to develop conditions for extracting metformin from biological fluids (blood and urine). The metformin solution extracted from biological fluids (blood and urine) was purified using thin-layer chromatography and then quantified by spectrophotometry. Under the recommended extraction conditions, metformin was extracted from blood and urine with average yields of 55.49% and 70.47%, respectively.

Conclusions: The results indicate that the developed method can be applied to extract metformin from biological fluids (blood, urine) in cases of acute poisoning with metformin.

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